

File name: fog_network
Author: Bartosz Kopras
Type of file: pdf
Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962446>
Size: 44 KB

File name: scenario_with_allocation
Author: Bartosz Kopras
Type of file: pdf
Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962446>
Size: 41 KB

File name: betaSweepCorrectedRate3000Reps14pt
Author: Bartosz Kopras
Type of file: pdf
Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962446>
Size: 32 KB
Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, “Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: cdfDelay700Both
Author: Bartosz Kopras
Type of file: pdf
Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962446>
Size: 265 KB
Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, “Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: complexitySweepCorrectedRate1000RepsFull2
Author: Bartosz Kopras
Type of file: pdf
Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962446>
Size: 50 KB
Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, “Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: delaySweepCorrectedRate10000Reps480-2-1000msNoCW

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: pdf

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962446>

Size: 49 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, "Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: histogram4reqsTo30

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: pdf

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962446>

Size: 26 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, "Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: sizeSweepCorrectedRate10000Reps005step

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: pdf

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962446>

Size: 44 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, "Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: basei5nolosses

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: m

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962427>

Size: 4 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, "Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: basei5withLosses

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: m

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962427>

Size: 6 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, "Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: bigResultsjointNewer

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: m

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962427>

Size: 2670 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, "Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: compli5withLosses

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: m

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962427>

Size: 10 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, "Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: delayReqi5withLosses2

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: m

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962427>

Size: 3 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, "Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: matEnergy05

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: mat

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962427>

Size: 25 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, “Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: matEnergy13

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: mat

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962427>

Size: 25 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, “Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.

File name: sizei5withLosses

Author: Bartosz Kopras

Type of file: m

Location: <https://zenodo.org/record/7962427>

Size: 6 KB

Tool: MATLAB

Generated based on Chapter 4 in B. Kopras, F. Idzikowski, B. Bossy, P. Kryszkiewicz, and H. Bogucka, “Communication and Computing Task Allocation for Energy-Efficient Fog Networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 997, Jan. 2023.
